

Debugging HPC Applications

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> **Overview**

- Benefits of using debuggers
- Basics of mdb (MPI-aware debugger)
- Live Demo of mdb

6 STAGES OF DEBUGGING

> What is a debugger?

A program used to test (or **debug**) another “**target**” program. The target program is run in a controlled environment that allows the user to inspect resources, interrupt program flow and even modify code execution.

> Can't I just use `printf()`?

> **Can't I just use `printf()`?**

✓ Valid if code cannot run without optimization

> Can't I just use `printf()`?

- ✓ Valid if code cannot run without optimization
- ✗ Requires recompiling code
- ✗ Could introduce new bugs
- ✗ Want to see a new variable?
 - Recompile again :(
- Cannot interactively alter runtime
- ✗

> Current Landscape of MPI Debuggers

features &
support

money

Introducing

mdb . . .

[logo coming soon...]

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mdb

> Key Features

- Terminal-based (debug local to code)
- Can use multiple backends (gdb/lldb)
- Uses python's [asyncio](#) library
- Can provide holistic analysis (plot)
- Scriptable
- Free and Open-Source

[github.com/TomMelt/mdb]

> **Live Demo**

- how does mdb work?
- where to get help (man/rtd/github)
- help command (?)
- plot
- broadcast
- mdb scripts

> Benefits of mdb

- Use all your favourite gdb/lldb commands!
- Debug HPC code where it lives
- Scriptable MPI debug sessions
- Debug 100-1000s of ranks (no extra \$\$\$)
- Holistic commands
- Beautiful ascii plots
- Ctrl-C is handled correctly (intel gdb 😍)
- (coming soon - debug parties 👁️)
- (coming soonish - TUI mode) 🎉

> **Other tools**

- `vscode (serial)`
- `vim/emacs plug-ins (serial)`
- [Intel's gdb](#)
- github.com/mystery-e204/mpidb
- github.com/Azrael3000/tmpi
- github.com/robertu94/mpigdb
- [Linaro ddt](#) (proprietary/license)
- [TotalView](#) (proprietary/license)
- ...

Special Thanks to:

@fjebaker

github.com/TomMelt/mdb

mdb.readthedocs.io/

